

Social Marketing: An Overview of Approach and Effects

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Abstract

This paper reviews the applicability of commercial and social marketing to teen driving safety. It draws on a wide range of information including evaluation studies of specific programs as well as standards of practice with in these two professions. Social marketing has been widely applied for more than three decades in the fields of public health, environmental protection, and political marketing with significant success. The paper attempts to distinguish between the practice of commercial marketing, whose goal is profit, and the practice of social marketing, whose goal is the societal benefit. The paper suggests the social marketing represents a viable companion to behavior change to promote teen driving safety and types of social marketing. Nowadays, social marketing principles being used in developing countries in areas such as health promotion, population control environment conservation, economic development, racism and human rights. Social marketing is not a new phenomenon as its roots can be seen in development strategies, social reform campaigns in olden days.

Keywords: Behavior, Driving, Social Marketing, Teen.

Introduction

Marketing being a social and managerial process, it must have a social, environmental approach unfortunately very few business organizations cared for it. Social marketing came into being as a separate discipline in the 1970s as a result of the acceptance of the environmental approach by the western countries. Now a day, social marketing principles are being used in developing countries in areas such as health promotion, population, control environment conservation, economic development, racism and human rights.

Social Marketing Concept

According to Kotler and al (2005). “The Societal [social] marketing concept holds the needs, wants, and interests of target markets and to deliver the desired satisfactions more effectively and efficiently than competitors in a way that preserves or enhances the consumes and the society’s wellbeing.”

Examples of Societal Marketing

Societal marketing is a concept in marketing that emphasizes social consciousness as part of the overall marketing plan. Societal marketing is when a company markets a product not only with consumer and company needs in mind but also the long-term well-being of society as a whole. Companies that produce effective societal marketing campaigns incorporate social and ethical considerations into the marketing plan. There are many ways a company can accomplish this goal.

Types of Social Marketing: Organisational

Universities, Government and non-government organizations, cooperative bodies are some examples of organizations engaged in social marketing. Government organizations may work at central, state, and local (municipal bodies and panchayat) levels. The central Government markets defense, civil and postal services. Universities, college and Government schools market educational services. Non-government organizations like Indian Cancer Society, CRY, Salads, FICCI, etc. Market ideas and charitable causes.

People Based: Individuals such as political candidates seek votes; volunteers seek donations etc.

Place-Based: Convention centers, industrial sites.

Idea Based: Family planning, AIDS control, no smoking, and other ideas are marketed.

Service Based: Education, child-care, community services and library services are some examples of service based marketing. The success of social marketing cannot be measured in financial terms. The number of clients served, quality of service, benefits provided are some criteria that can be based to judge the efficiency of social marketing.

Societal Marketing Purpose and Strategy

The purpose of societal marketing is for a company to meet its needs and the needs of the consumer while considering the long-term good of society. In this type of marketing, a company uses its socially conscious stance as a way to attract consumers who may appreciate the company's desire to market its products with consideration for society, seemingly over profit, positions the company in a favorable light and may help sell more products.

Consumer Health

Marketing campaigns that emphasize consumer health are campaigns that fall into the societal marketing strategy. Companies that market organic ingredients or no chemicals or additives in their products consider consumer health in making their products. This concern for consumer health becomes a strong point in the marketing process.

Eco-Friendly Marketing

Companies that emphasize recycled products and organic products that aren't going to damage the ozone layer fall under the societal marketing strategy. Companies that make products from recycled materials can market themselves as a company concerned about the long-term impact on society.

Prospects for Social Marketing

In 21-century social marketing, principles could certainly benefit the organization (i.e., Social, educational, health, political and business), the consumer and socio-economic and an environment system. Information technology has made communication system very dynamic, interactive and effective. So the whole world has become a 'Global Village.'

Supporting Farms and Local Business

Companies that don't import raw materials practice a more contained form of societal marketing by marketing products made with materials obtained from local sources. This type of marketing takes into account the well-being of the local social structure. A company that purchases raw materials from local farmers or other businesses can market its products using this fact as a key part of its marketing strategy.

Application of Social Marketing

In recent years social marketing attracting the interest of non-profit institutions like educational institutions, hospitals, govt organizations and non-govt organizations for marketing their services. Social marketing has a wider scope. Social marketing techniques have been used successfully in health promotion programmes such as family welfare, heart care, human organ donations, physical fitness, immunization awareness against AIDS, smoking and drinking.

Social marketing techniques are being applied in important areas such as the provision of safe drinking water, soil, conservation, preservation of wild life forestation, protection of environment etc.

Social leaders have been applying social marketing strategies in areas like protection of human rights abolition of casteism and racism. Since the 1970s the western countries have accepted the environmental approach to developmental strategies. Business organization has been applying social marketing techniques for implementation of their business policies satisfying consumers, long-term welfare of the society, attracting investors, motivating and training the workers.

The developmental strategies adopted so far are responsible for all sorts of pollution (i.e., air, water, sound, etc.) Imbalanced ecology and have endangered the very existence of human beings. For example, detergents used for cloth washing is responsible for water pollution and loss of aquatic lives. Popular plastic products are not disposable and create environmental problems. All sorts of vehicles add to air and sound pollution, on the contrary, the govt has to spend crores of rupees on oil import bill.

Some research studies have shown that consumables like tobacco products, injuries, cosmetics are injurious to health. Still injurious products are being poured into the market. McDonalds and Kentucky, the pioneers of 'Fast food culture', are making huge profits at the cost of consumer health.

The indifferent attitude of marketers has bought irreparable loss to human life and the universe. Wrong marketing strategies are resulting in creating health problems, slims, pollution and ecological imbalance, the cost of which must be borne by the organizations making a huge profit.

Prospects for Social Marketing

In the 21st-century social marketing principles could certainly benefit the organization (i.e., social, educational, health, political and business) the consumers and change the socio-economic and an environment system, information technology has made communication system very dynamic, interactive and effective.

So the whole world has become a 'Global village.' In the world of marshal goldsmith "new technologies, new organization and the global village will have a propound effect on our sense of community in the years ahead.

Two trends stand out the explosion of our potential to communicate instantaneously and mass across the globe and closely aligned with our ability to create communities of our choice".

In future social marketers will have to adopt information technology to build rapport with target groups, gaining the support of the masses to social reform campaigns, health promotion campaigns and creating awareness regarding environment protection for themselves and future generations.

Conclusion

Social marketing is applying the world over and India is no exception. This concept has altered the traditional concept of marketing society oriented development strategy can be helpful in overcoming the serious problems like pollutions, explosion, ecological imbalance, the world over poverty, imbalanced development and meeting the basic needs, e.g., drinking water, food and shelter, education and healthcare.

Social marketing can be applied in any sphere of life and can help in enriching the life of human being and care for the safety of the universe. The explosion of information technology makes communication very dynamic.

The leaders of social change will have to adopt information technology for communication is interacting and confidence building among masses.

Let us hope the Indian development policies have the essence of social principles linked with non-pollution and ecology in the interest of present and future generations.

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